

Metal Chelates of Phenylhydrazonothenoyltrifluoroacetone

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Aryldiazonium ion reacts with 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds to form intramolecularly hydrogen bonded 1,2,3-tricarbonyl-2-arylhydrazones rather than the 2-aryloxo tautomer¹⁻³. Besides having wide application as yellow dyes and pigments, these products have been extensively used as intermediates in the preparation of a large number of biologically important compounds. Transition metal complexes of several non-fluorinated 1,3-dicarbonyl-2-arylhydrazones have been reported earlier^{3,4}. The present communication reports the synthesis and characterisation of metal chelates of phenylhydrazonothenoyltrifluoroacetone, Hptta, (systematic name: 1-(2-thienyl)-4,4,4-trifluoro-1,3-butanedione-2-phenylhydrazone).

Results and Discussion

All the metal complexes (Table 1) are non-conducting (specific conductance, $10 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and do not contain the metal salt used for their preparation. The Ni and Pd complexes are diamagnetic. The magnetic moment of Cu^{II} , Co^{II} and VO^{II} complexes are 1.82, 4.88 and 1.72 B.M. respectively. UV, ir and ^1H nmr spectral data of Hptta conform to the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded hydrazone form in which the thenoyl carbonyl is hydrogen bonded with the hydrazone NH, leaving the trifluoroacetyl carbonyl free. Thus the ir spectrum shows two strong bands at 1705 and 1640 cm^{-1} assignable respectively to the stretching of the free trifluoroacetyl carbonyl and the hydrogen bonded thenoyl carbonyl^{2,3}. A considerably broad band in the region 3500–2800 cm^{-1} is also observed in the spectrum due to the chelated NH group. A

comparison with the ir spectra of phenylhydrazonoacetylacetone^{2,8} and thenoyltrifluoroacetone⁵ reveals that the medium intensity bands appeared in the spectrum of Hptta at 1520, 1435 and 1410 cm^{-1} are due to the stretching of the thienyl ring and the two strong bands at 1295 and 1010 cm^{-1} due to the CF_3 group. The ^1H nmr spectrum consists of a low-field one-proton signal at δ 13.60 characteristic of $-\text{N}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}=\text{C}$ group^{2,8}. The aryl proton signals appeared at δ 6.80–7.80 as a complex multiplet.

The values of the uv absorption maxima given for the free ligand (Table 1) are associated with the carbonyl and hydrazo groups⁶. The fact that in the complexes these bands have undergone a shift to longer wavelengths, indicates that these groups are involved in the chelating process. Infrared spectra of the metal complexes are compatible with the structure that would result if the chelated hydrazone NH is replaced by metal ion as in structure 1.

M = Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , VO^{II} , Pd^{II}

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)				λ_{max} (nm)	ν_{max} (cm^{-1})		
		C	H	N	M		Chelated CO	M—N	M—O
1.	Hptta (Yellow)	50.80 (51.30)	2.28 (2.76)	8.10 (8.59)	—	265, 330	1 640	—	—
2.	$\text{Cu}(\text{ptta})_2$ (Dark brown)	46.98 (47.09)	2.32 (2.52)	7.81 (7.85)	8.67 (8.80)	285, 348	1 575	538	427
3.	$\text{Ni}(\text{ptta})_2$ (Dark green)	47.10 (47.41)	2.31 (2.54)	7.83 (7.90)	8.03 (8.90)	282, 348	1 572	540	428
4.	$\text{Co}(\text{ptta})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ (Yellow brown)	45.02 (45.10)	2.42 (2.38)	7.48 (7.52)	7.84 (7.91)	280, 345	1 573	554	425
5.	$\text{VO}(\text{ptta})_2$ (Dark red)	46.58 (46.81)	2.45 (2.51)	7.78 (7.81)	7.02 (7.11)	278, 345	1 570	555	423
6.	$\text{Pd}(\text{ptta})_2$ (Dark)	44.05 (44.42)	2.32 (2.12)	7.18 (7.40)	—	288, 347	1 568	535	420

Thus the position of the free ligand band at 1705 cm^{-1} is only marginally altered ($\pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the metal complexes. The band at 1640 cm^{-1} due to the hydrogen bonded thenoyl carbonyl of the ligand, disappeared in the spectra of the complexes. Instead, a new band appeared at $\sim 1570\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 1) in the spectra of all the metal complexes. This band can be assigned to the stretching of the metal-bonded carbonyl function^{3,5}. A weak band attributable to conjugated $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ appeared at $\sim 1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the metal chelates. In the spectrum of the ligand this band is presumably masked by the strong absorption of the thenoyl carbonyl occurring in the same region. The broad band of the ligand at $3500\text{--}2800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ cleared up in the spectra of the metal chelates. A weak band at $\sim 3050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to aromatic ν_{CH} was also observed in the spectra of the chelates. A broad band at 3590 cm^{-1} due to coordinated water was observed in the spectrum of the Co^{II} complex. The band due to the CF_3 group of the ligand remained almost unaffected in the spectra of the chelates. The characteristic band due to the thenoyl ring shifted to lower frequencies in the spectra of all the metal chelates. Spectra of all the metal chelates showed two medium intensity bands at $530\text{--}570$ and $\sim 425\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\text{M}-\text{N}$ and $\text{M}-\text{O}$ stretching respectively^{3,5}. In the Co^{II} chelate an additional band observed at 418 cm^{-1} is presumably due to $\nu_{\text{Co}\leftarrow\text{OH}_2}$ vibration⁷. In the spectrum of the VO^{II} complex a band at 982 cm^{-1} was observed due to $\text{V}=\text{O}$ stretch.

In the ^1H nmr spectra of the diamagnetic Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} chelates, the low-field signal of the ligand at $\delta 13.60$ disappeared, which indicates the replacement of the NH proton during metal chelation. The integrated intensities of the aryl proton signals ($\delta 6.8\text{--}7.5$) of the chelates agree well with their formulation.

Substitution of trifluoromethyl group increases the volatility of metal 1,3-diketones. Thus fluoro-1,3-diketone chelates have been the most extensively studied class of compounds in the gas chromatographic measurement of metal ions due to their high volatility and excellent thermal and solvolytic stability^{8,9}. However, unlike the chelates of thenoyl-trifluoroacetone, thermograms of the chelates of Hptta obtained in nitrogen atmosphere, show that these chelates undergo decomposition below 200° (the decomposition began at temperatures ($^\circ\text{C}$) 185, 182, 170, 168 and 165 respectively, for Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , VO^{II} and Pd^{II} chelates). This is probably

due to the interference of the bulky aryl groups and the free trifluoroacetyl group on the stability of the chelate ring.

Experimental

Hptta was prepared through the coupling of phenyldiazonium chloride (1 mmol) with thenoyl-trifluoroacetone (1 mmol) in aqueous methanol (50%, v/v) at pH 6–7, and the product was recrystallised from hot ethanol^{1,2}. For preparing metal complexes, a concentrated aqueous solution of the metal salt (1 mmol; acetate of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and chlorides of VO^{II} , Pd^{II}) was added to a stirred solution (50 ml) of the ligand (2 mmol) in methanol. The solution was heated on a water-bath for about 1 h and then cooled in ice. The precipitated complex was filtered, washed with ethanol, and recrystallised from hot ethanol.

Molar conductance of the complexes in ethanol (10^{-3} M) was measured on a Thoshniwal conductivity bridge. Uv spectra were recorded on a Car Zeiss DMR spectrophotometer, ir spectra on a Pye-Unicam SP 3000 instrument and ^1H nmr spectra on a Varian EM 360 L spectrometer. C, H, N and metal contents were done by standard methods. Thermograms were obtained from a Dupont 990 thermal analyser. Magnetic susceptibility measurement was carried out at room temperature by the Gouy method.

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